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TWO CHANNELS ROBUST DETECTOR OF A RADAR FOR RESCUERS

Subject and purpose. The research focuses on robust signal processing methods in environments with partially known noise characteristics, and explores possible algorithms for their implementation. The primary emphasis is on analyzing the spectral properties of interference and evaluating their impact on algorithms used to detect and identify radar information signals. These signals are specifically designed to locate living individuals in the aftermath of man-made or natural disasters. The objective of this work is to develop a robust detector that ensures fast and reliable detection of radar information signals, even under conditions of prior uncertainty regarding the spectral characteristics of the interference.

Method and methodology. The research methods rely on robust mathematical statistics, which underpin an algorithm designed to detect a pseudo-random phase-shift keyed signal amidst additive noise with partially unknown spectral characteristics. The methodology involves analyzing the detection system's sensitivity to deviations in the spectral characteristics of both signals and interference from the models that form the basis of the detection algorithm.

Results. In addressing the challenge of synthesizing a robust signal detector under uncertainty in the statistical characteristics of interference, an algorithm has been developed for detecting phase-coded manipulated signals in short-range radar systems. This algorithm is designed to be insensitive to deviations in the actual spectral characteristics of interference from the nominal model. This robustness is achieved through a two-channel signal processing circuit, where the optimization of the frequency response for the main and compensation channels is based on different criteria. In the main channel, each elementary pulse of a pseudo-random sequence is evaluated using the criterion of minimum mean square error, while the frequency response of the compensation channel is optimized according to the criterion of minimum noise dispersion.

Conclusion. Analytical expressions have been derived for the optimal frequency characteristics of the main and compensation channels of a robust detector, operating under conditions of a priori uncertainty regarding the spectral characteristics of interference. It is demonstrated that the minimum possible error when estimating pulses of a phase-coded manipulated signal using the Mersenne code in the proposed two-channel processing procedure is lower than in the optimal classical scheme designed for the Gaussian noise model. The proposed two-channel structure of the signal processing algorithm is a universal procedure, as it allows optimization of both the main and compensation channels according to different criteria. This versatility enables the development of adaptive algorithms based on this structure. However, the proposed scheme does have a drawback: hardware redundancy.

Keywords: Pseudo-Noise Modulation, Noise, Algorithm, Pulse Modulation, Mersenne code, Robust Detector, Rescuer Radar, Opaque Obstacles.

Introduction

The task of detecting a living person behind optically opaque obstacles using radio methods is generally the task of detecting a known type of signal with observations containing noise. In particular, works [1 - 4] show that pseudo-random phase-coded Mersenne keyed signals [5, 6] are quite effective in these applications. However, when the radar operates in real conditions, reflections of the sounding signal from obstacles and local objects, multipath propagation, etc., create a complex interference environment. In this case, the classical representation of interference as a fluctuation process with previously known statistical characteristics is not an adequate model. As a result, the optimal detection algorithm, in the sense of maximum likelihood, significantly reduces its effectiveness or even produces erroneous results. So, it will be advisable to build a detection algorithm based on nonparametric statistical methods [7, 8].

Let's assume that the signal and passive interference have finite energies over the observation interval

T , and their spectral densities are concentrated within a finite frequency interval

ΔF . Without loss of generality, the fluctuation component of the noise can be represented by a Gaussian process with zero average value and constant spectral density within the frequency band ΔF . For pseudo-random quasi-continuous Mersenne signals with a sequence length of several tens of thousands of elements, the relation is valid $\Delta FT \gg 1$. Therefore, the error caused by the finite approximation of signals $S(t)$ and noise $\eta(t)$ is negligible. Obviously, the specific type of implementation of passive interference in each observation should be considered unknown. Based on the assumptions made, the detection problem can be formulated in the following generalized form. It is necessary to synthesize a rule for detecting a signal $S(t)$, for which the probability of a false alarm and correct detection are invariant with respect to the $\eta(t)$

interference, and the probability of detection is maximum for any signal/fluctuation noise ratio.

The traditional solution to such a problem comes down to the synthesis of an optimal matched filter [9, 10], the characteristics of which are calculated based on accurate information about the signal shape and the noise correlation function. However, with unknown noise characteristics, optimal detection algorithms may lead to errors in the form of singular detection. The essence of this phenomenon is that the estimate of the signal-to-noise ratio at the output of such a detector can become infinitely large, which obviously does not correspond to the real situation. The likelihood of such a problem occurring is especially high when using Mersenne code modulation of the radar sounding signal. The shape of the spectral density $S(j\omega)$ envelope of such a signal is close to rectangular. The spectral density of noise $N(j\omega)$ passing through the selective circuits of the receiver has a shape close to triangular. Then it turns out that the frequency response $S^*(j\omega)/N(j\omega)$ of the optimal matched filter increases infinitely as the frequency approaches to values $\pm\omega_0$. The signal-to-noise ratio q at the output of the optimal filter will be

$$q = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\omega_0}^{\omega_0} \frac{|S(j\omega)|^2}{N(j\omega)} d\omega \quad (1)$$

Small deviations of the signal shape from the calculated one lead to sudden changes q from infinity to zero. It is possible to reduce sensitivity to deviations of the signal shape from the calculated one if the optimal detection algorithm is based on the smallest possible value of the bandwidth. Such an algorithm will be highly efficient with a minimum signal bandwidth and extremely low sensitivity to its deviations from the ω_0 value.

1. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM OF SYNTHESIS OF A ROBUST DETECTOR

A signal modulated in phase by the Mersenne code is a continuous sequence of radio pulses $p(t)$ of different durations, the phase of which differs by $\pm\pi$. The observed implementation of a mixture of signal and noise in general form can be written as follows

$$y(t) = \gamma \sum_{i=1}^m a_i p_i(t) + \eta_i(t), \quad m = 2^k - 1, \quad (2)$$

where $p_i(t) = p(t - (i-1)T)$ – is the base impulse $p(t)$, delayed at $(i-1)T$, γ – is the average amplitude of the pulse sequence, k – Mersenne code parameter, which determines the length of the non-repeating pulse sequence.

In accordance with the maximum likelihood method [9, 11], solving the problem of synthesizing an

optimal detection algorithm is reduced to testing statistical hypotheses $H_0 : \gamma = \gamma_0$ and $H_1 : \gamma = \gamma_1$. In this case, the generalized structure of the optimal detector consists of a set of matched filters for each partial pulse of the sequence and a coherent storage device over the duration interval T of the entire sequence. In general, the output of each matched partial filter has the maximum signal-to-noise ratio achievable by a linear filter. The frequency response $G(\omega)$ of the filter has the form

$$G(j\omega) = \frac{S_p^*(j\omega)}{N(j\omega)} e^{-j\omega t}, \quad (3)$$

where $S_p^*(j\omega)$ – is the Fourier transform for pulse $p_i(t)$.

The general expression for the signal-to-noise ratio at the output of a filter with frequency characteristic $G(j\omega)$, at time T , when the implementation of the process $\gamma p(t) + \eta(t)$ is applied to its input, has the form

$$q = \frac{\left| \frac{\gamma}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} G(j\omega) S(j\omega) e^{j\omega t} d\omega \right|^2}{\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |G(j\omega)|^2 N(j\omega) d\omega}. \quad (4)$$

The maximum value of the gain value q from equation (4) is achieved when the frequency response of the filter and the spectrum of the signal exactly correspond. However, the real signal is usually distorted. A measure of distortion can be the integral of the squared difference between the momenta $p(t)$ and $p_0(t)$ or between their spectra $S(j\omega)$ and $S_0(j\omega)$. Then, as a model of signal uncertainty for a given problem, one can specify a class of pulses $\mathfrak{T} \in \{p(t)\}$ whose Fourier transform $S(j\omega)$ satisfies the condition

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |S(j\omega) - S_0(j\omega)|^2 d\omega \leq \Delta, \quad (5)$$

where $S_0(j\omega)$ – is Fourier transform of undistorted pulse, Δ – is a parameter that specifies the permissible degree of distortion.

An optimization problem of the form $\max\{\min(q)\}$, where q was defined from (4), has the following solution [12, 13]

$$\hat{G}(j\omega) = \frac{S_0^*(j\omega) e^{-j\omega t}}{N(j\omega) + \sigma_0}, \quad (6)$$

where the positive constant σ_0 depends on the Δ (in the general case it is a monotonic function of the Δ).

As can be seen from (3) and (6), in the robust filter for the uncertainty model (5), the gain at frequencies where the noise power is low is limited compared to its value for the optimal matched filter. In other words, the higher gain of the optimal filter at extreme frequencies makes it too sensitive to such deviations in the characteristics of the pulse, which lead to a decrease in its energy at these frequencies. The uncertainty in the signal is taken into account by robust filters by including an

additional component in the noise spectrum, with the help of which it becomes possible to adjust the sensitivity of the system with respect to possible distortions of the observed signals. It is possible to implement in practice the continuous process of detecting a sequence of Mersenne code pulses using a two-channel scheme.

2. Two-channel implementation of a robust detector FOR rescue radar

We will pass each pulse of the Mersenne code sequence through the following two-channel filter circuit in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. A two-channel filter circuit.

The filter input receives a mixture of signal and noise, which is distributed into two channels. The channels have amplifiers with complex gains $B(j\omega)$ and $K(j\omega)$, respectively. The optimal transfer function of such a scheme can be found based on the criterion of minimum mean square error [14]

$$\varepsilon = E\{\hat{p}(t) - p_0(t)\}, \tag{7}$$

where $E\{\cdot\}$ – is expectation symbol, $\hat{p}(t)$ – pulse estimation.

The solution to optimization problem (7) $\arg \min\{\varepsilon\}$ gives the filter transfer function

$$K(j\omega) = \frac{S(j\omega)[K_{11}(j\omega) - B(j\omega)K_{12}(j\omega)]^*}{|K_{11}(j\omega) - B(j\omega)K_{12}(j\omega)|^2 S(j\omega) + |K_{21}(j\omega) - B(j\omega)K_{22}(j\omega)|^2 G(j\omega)}, \tag{8}$$

where $K_{11}(j\omega), K_{12}(j\omega), K_{21}(j\omega), K_{22}(j\omega)$ – are the transfer function estimates.

In this case, the value of the root-mean-square error can be calculated using the formula

$$\varepsilon^2 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{S(j\omega)G(j\omega)}{G(j\omega) + \frac{|K_{11}(j\omega) - B(j\omega)K_{12}(j\omega)|^2}{|K_{21}(j\omega) - B(j\omega)K_{22}(j\omega)|^2} S(j\omega)} d\omega. \tag{9}$$

As follows from (9), the root mean square error can be minimized by choosing the optimal value of the transfer function of compensating channel $B(j\omega)$ from the following condition

$$K(j\omega) = 0.5 + \sqrt{0.25 - |K_{21}(j\omega) - B(j\omega)K_{22}(j\omega)|^2 \frac{G(j\omega)}{S(j\omega)}}. \tag{10}$$

In the special case when the $|K_{11}(j\omega)| \square |K_{12}(j\omega)|$ optimal transfer function of the compensating channel will be determined by the system of equations

$$\begin{cases} |B(j\omega)| = |K_{21}(j\omega)| + |K_{22}(j\omega)|^{-1} \sqrt{\left(1 - |K_{11}(j\omega)|\right) |K_{11}(j\omega)| \frac{S(j\omega)}{G(j\omega)}}, \\ \varphi_B(\omega) = \varphi_{21}(\omega) - \varphi_{22}(\omega) \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where $\varphi_{21}(\omega)$ and $\varphi_{22}(\omega)$ are the arguments of transfer characteristics $K_{21}(j\omega)$ and $K_{22}(j\omega)$ respectively.

The value of the root mean square error, in this case, will be determined by the following formula

$$\min \left\{ E \left[\varepsilon^2 \right] \right\} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |S(\omega) - S_{0x}(\omega)|^2 d\omega, \quad (12)$$

where $S_{0x}(\omega)$ – is cross spectral density of functions $p(t)$ and $p_0(t)$.

Theoretically, the minimum possible value of the root mean square error is zero.

Conclusion. Thus, the introduction of a compensation channel makes it possible to increase the filtering properties of the system compared to conventional filters. The gain in noise immunity of this system is explained by the fact that in addition to the differences in the properties of $S(j\omega)$ and $G(j\omega)$, it uses differences in the characteristics of the signal and interference in the main and compensation channels. The most significant case in this sense is when the condition is satisfied $G(j\omega) \square S(j\omega)$. At the output of the Wiener filter, the mean square error is given by the equation

$$\varepsilon^2 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S(\omega) d\omega. \quad (13)$$

Comparing relations (12) and (13) taking into account the condition $S_{0x}(\omega) = |K_{11}(j\omega)| S(\omega) \geq 0$

, it can be concluded that $\varepsilon_{\min}^2 \leq \varepsilon^2$. In other words, the considered robust system under the specified conditions makes it possible to realize a smaller mean square error compared to the Wiener filter. The introduction of a compensation channel also allows you to further regulate the efficiency of the system by optimizing the transfer function of the compensation channel $B(j\omega) = K_{21}(j\omega) K_{22}^{-1}(j\omega)$. In addition, the compensation channel allows you to separate signal processing operations in the main channel and in the interference suppression channel, and the characteristics of the compensation channel can be optimized according to some noise immunity criterion, and the main one can be optimized, for example, according to the efficiency criterion, depending on the problem being solved by the system.

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